

Supporting Information: Molecular Beam Epitaxy of GaN Nanowires on Epitaxial Graphene Layer Structures

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Extended Raman spectrum of the Type III graphene layer structure after GaN growth

Figure S1 presents the μ -Raman spectra covering the complete spectral range of first- and second-order scattering by optical phonons for the Type III graphene layer structure (GLS III) prior to and after GaN growth. In both cases, we have subtracted the contribution of the SiC substrate. For the sample after GaN growth, the GaN contribution was also subtracted. The μ -Raman spectra of the SiC substrate and the GaN film used to subtract the corresponding background signals are shown in Figure S1 for the sake of completeness. The pristine GLS III exhibits the characteristic 2D and G peaks of graphene. The D peak, which is known to be caused by the presence of structural defects (see main manuscript), is basically absent. After the growth of GaN nanowires (NWs) on the GLS III, we observe a decrease in the intensity of the 2D peak and the appearance of a weak D peak. The decrease in the intensity of the 2D peak as well as the development of the D peak, related to structural defects, are attributed to the etching of the graphene layer structure during GaN growth by the active N species generated by the radio-frequency

Figure S1: Raman spectra for the GLS III prior to (GLS III) and after GaN growth (GLS III + GaN). The spectra of the SiC substrate and the GaN film used to subtract the SiC and GaN contributions from the original Raman spectra are also shown for comparison. All the spectra are vertically shifted for clarity.

Figure S2: (a)-(d) High-resolution transmission electron micrographs of regions in between GaN NWs for the sample prepared on the GLS III.

Figure S3: (a) Bright-field cross-sectional transmission electron micrograph of a representative GaN NW from the ensemble prepared on the GLS III. (b) High-resolution transmission electron micrograph acquired along the $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle$ zone axis in a middle section of the NW shown in (a). (c) Fourier transform of the micrograph shown in (b). (d) and (e) Lattice images taken within the NW section shown in (b). The region presented in (e) corresponds approximately to the area indicated by a red square in (d). The micrographs shown in (d) and (e) were Fourier filtered to remove high-frequency noise.

Figure S4: (a) Bird's eye scanning electron micrograph of GaN NWs grown on the GLS III. The numerical labels indicate typical nucleation sites at step edges (1) and scratches (2), respectively. (b) Representative CL spectra recorded at the regions indicated in (a) at 10 K.

N plasma-source.

Additional transmission electron micrographs of the Type III graphene layer structure after GaN growth

Figure S2 presents high-resolution transmission electron micrographs with different magnifications of regions in between GaN NWs for the sample prepared on the GLS III. As shown in Figure S2(a), the remaining graphene layer structure after GaN growth is perfectly continuous. At certain places, see Figure S2(b), we detect the wrinkles that were previously observed by atomic force microscopy in the pristine structure, as discussed in the main manuscript. The total thickness of the remaining graphene layers varies, depending on the region and the micrograph, between 3.5 and 7 nm. Interestingly, due to sample preparation for transmission electron microscopy studies, the graphene structure tends to detach from the substrate as can be clearly observed in Figures S2(a), S2(c) and S2(d).

Transmission electron micrographs of a representative GaN nanowire grown on the Type III graphene layer structure

The morphology and crystallinity of the GaN NWs grown on the GLS III were further investigated by transmission electron microscopy. Figure S3(a) shows a bright-field scanning transmission electron micrograph of a 1.9 μm long and uncoalesced GaN NW. The NW has flat top and sidewall facets, and a diameter of about 100 nm. The varying contrast along the NW axis is a strain contour caused by the unintentional bending of the NWs during sample preparation. Most NWs were found to be free of stacking faults, a result consistent with the photoluminescence spectrum shown in Figure 5. Figure S3(b) presents a high-resolution transmission electron micrograph of a section of the NW shown in Figure S3(a). In this micrograph, there are no stacking faults and its corresponding Fourier transform, shown in Figure S3(c), confirms the single crystal nature of the NW and demonstrate that it crystallized in the wurtzite modification (as expected according to the x-ray diffraction, Raman, and photoluminescence experiments reported in the main manuscript). Finally, the highly magnified high-resolution transmission electron micrographs shown in Figures S3(d) and

S3(e) resolve the lattice of the wurtzite structure and attest to the high crystallinity of this representative GaN NW.

Cathodoluminescence spectra of GaN nanowires grown on the Type III graphene layer structure

Figure S4(a) presents a typical bird's eye scanning electron micrograph of the GaN NWs grown on the GLS III. The NWs nucleate predominantly either at step edges (see label 1) or scratches (see label 2). Cathodoluminescence (CL) spectra of three different regions in Figure S4(a) are depicted in Figure S4(b). Spectra A, B, and C show a prominent line around 3.472 eV attributed to the recombination of excitons bound to neutral donors $[(D^0,X)]$ in unstrained GaN. Spectra B and C also show a peak around 3.42 eV related to the recombination of excitons at I_1 stacking faults $[(I_1,X)]$. Beside these peaks, we also observe at 3.27 eV, a donor-acceptor pair transition (DAP), together with its longitudinal optical (LO) phonon replicas at 3.17 and 3.08 eV. The relative variation in the intensity of the (I_1,X) and DAP peaks in respect to the $[(D^0,X)]$ transition is attributed to random fluctuations across the NW ensemble in the density of stacking faults. Regardless of where NWs nucleate, at step edges or scratches, all these spectral features are found to be characteristic for the GaN NWs grown on the GLS III. Finally, it is important to note that, when the NW ensembles are analyzed by CL, the quenching of the (D^0,X) transition caused by the unintentional deposition of hydrocarbons leads to an increase in the $(I_1,X)/(D^0,X)$ and $DAP/(D^0,X)$ intensity ratios as compared to photoluminescence measurements.